

Systematic Investment Plan - Mutual Fund

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Abstract

To state in simple words, a mutual fund collects the savings from small investors, invest them in government and other corporate securities and earn income through interest and dividends, besides capital gains. It works on the principle of ‘small drops of water make a big ocean’. SIP investment is investing a fixed amount of money every month in a mutual fund of investors choice. This is ideally suited to people who save a fixed amount of money every month and want to invest as and when they earn instead of waiting for the money to accumulate.

Introduction

In India, there are a large number of mutual funds. All mutual funds are under the regulatory framework of the Securities Exchange Board of India with exception of Unit Trust of India (UTI). The income and capital appreciation arising out of investments are shared among investors. Their securities are subject to market risk. The investors should be aware of those risks while an investment decision. Even with risks the mutual funds are able to perform better than an individual because a careful selection of securities over a diversified portfolio covering large number of companies and industries is made and the portfolio is constantly reviewed.

Objectives of the Study

- To create awareness about Systematic Investment Plan (SIP).
- To study the best mutual funds for SIP.

Ways to Invest in Mutual Funds

There are two ways in mutual funds:

1. Lump Sum

Lump sum investment refers to a one-time investment of money. If investors have a large sum of money and wish to use it to earn more money, investors can invest it in one go in a mutual fund of their choice. By doing so, investors ensure that the amount is immediately mobilized to grow and generate more money for investors. This is ideal for when investors do not need the said amount for some time.

2. Systematic Investment Plan (SIP)

SIP investment is investing a fixed amount of money every month in a mutual fund of investors choice. This is ideally suited to people who save a fixed amount of money every month and want to invest

as and when they earn instead of waiting for the money to accumulate. SIP also offers investors the advantage of rupee cost averaging – which basically ensures investors do not pay a very high price to purchase units of mutual funds over a long period of time.

Systematic Investment Plan

It is based on the idea of recurring deposits where an investor invests a specific sum of money at frequent intervals like monthly or quarterly. In a way, SIP disregards the much-hyped idea of timing the market. SIP plans provide a systematic form of investment where an investor can organize or plan their investments to break into smaller payments rather than invest a huge lump-sum amount at one go. It provides a more viable mode of investment and makes the idea of investments less intimidating to the average person with lesser buying power. It enforces the importance of saving over years so that the investor can eventually reap the overall benefits of all the payments they have made towards the SIP. In addition to making investment more accessible to the average earner in the economy, it also benefits wealthy investors by saving them from the disappointments of wrong investments or untimely investments. SIPs offer ease of investment to the investors who agree to pay a certain amount of money towards the SIP every month. This amount is automatically debited from their account and invested in a mutual fund scheme. Depending on the NAV for the day, the amount investors pay is allocated towards buying certain units of the mutual fund. When money is paid the next month, another set of units for the mutual fund scheme is purchased and added to the current units. Since the mutual funds are purchased at different rates every time investors pay the SIP, investors benefit from the power of compounding and rupee-cost averaging.

What is Rupee Cost Averaging?

This term refers to the process of investing frequently without relying on the process of timing the market. This removes the need to guess the right time to invest and invest when the markets are low and sell the stocks when market prices are high.

Rupee-cost averaging is all about investing a certain amount of money without any relevance to the current market conditions. By using this technique, investors can offset the chances of a risk, although they may not be able to avoid risks completely.

For example, investors invest ₹ 500 every month in an SIP plan. Investors will be able to buy 20 units of a fund when the unit price is ₹25, but when the price falls to ₹20 in the next month, investors will be able to add 25 units of the same fund to their account. Investors would have paid an average cost of ₹22.5 for 45 units. This benefits investors from overpaying for the funds when the markets are high because investors investing in a fixed amount every month. So if the market prices are high then the total number of units bought that month will automatically be low. This is what rupee-cost averaging is.

Compounding

Compounding is the term used for the method through which interest is calculated on SIPs which leads to a substantial amount of savings after a period of time. A person begins INR.1000 a month at the age of 20. At the end of 30 years, when he turns 50, he will have accumulated a total sum of 35 lakhs compounded at 12% per annum. The word compounded here means that every year, interest was calculated for the total amount of money accumulated by the end of that year which includes the principle and the interest. Hence the compound amount of the principle and the interest grows at 12% per annum.

If the same person had started investing 5 years later, when he was 25, then by the time he turned 50 he would have a total sum of 16 lakhs compounded at the same rate of 12% per annum. The interesting part here is that the difference in the investment is 5 years' worth of investment which

comes to 60,000 but the amount gained at the end of the investment has a difference of a whopping 14 lakhs.

Since interest continues to get added to the principle, compounding usually generates better results over a long period of time. This also entails the fact the investments should begin at an early age. It helps the person save more over a certain number of years. Since most companies in India have a retirement age of around 60, investors would want to be able to save up through SIP by this time through a good SIP scheme. The early investors begin, the more they will be able to save by retirement.

Types of Investments in Sips

Most SIPs are based on monthly investments. This is because most of the investors are salaried people who are paid once a month. Agents who sell SIPs aggressively pitch in the monthly SIPs because of the popularity of this type of investment in SIPs. A lot of investors are comfortable with monthly payments as well so it is easier for agents to make conversions with monthly SIPs.

But there are other types of investment like Daily SIPs where investors invest on a daily basis. In daily SIP, the investor invests a certain sum of money every day to buy the fund at the NAV for the day. While some micro-investors may find this promising, it lacks the ease of monthly investments which is why it is less popular.

Quarterly and bi-annual SIPs allow investors to contribute a specific amount of money every quarter or once every six months. If monthly investments are over-burdening their financial position then investors may consider either of these for their SIP scheme.

A. Perpetual SIP: Like the name suggests, Perpetual SIP plans do not require any renewal. They go on for as long as investors want. This type of investment plan does not come with an end date. It means that investors have the opportunity to withdraw the SIP amount whenever investors want to. Many investors see this as a good opportunity to invest till the time they want instead of having to pay for a specified period of time according to the fund house. It gives more freedom to the investor in terms of choosing the period of time for which they want to make the investment.

B. Alert SIP: If investors like to time the market but investors prefer SIPs because of the ability to make small investments on a regular basis then the Alert SIP may be able to interest investors. The investor gets an alert when the market goes down so that they can invest when the market is low. People who have good knowledge about the market will be able to use this type of investment in SIPs to their advantage.

How to Invest in Sips?

Investments are a lot more streamlined now than what they were before. This makes it easy for investors to complete most of the documentation online and even buy the SIP online.

Begin with Completing the KYC Procedure

KYC stands for Know Your Customer. It is an important step for investing in any type of mutual funds. Since SIPs invest in mutual funds, investors must complete the KYC. It is a one-time exercise which will allow investors to begin their investment plans. This is a mandatory process which cannot be missed. Investors will be required to submit their Pan card, identity proof and address proof. The procedure is completed when their documents and physical existence are verified through In-Person verification (IPV). If investors submit their AADHAR card for the identity proof then investors will not have to complete the IPV. If investors do not submit their PAN card then their investments will be limited to INR.50,000 for a financial year. To make sure that investors do not face problems in future when they increase their investment amount, it is best

to submit their PAN card during the KYC process. Investors will have the opportunity to submit it anytime at a later date as well.

Provide Bank Details

Investors should keep bank details ready and make sure investors have their mobile phone with them because they will be required to enter their bank details at the time of the registration and investors must verify their account through the OTP sent to the mobile number investors register. Once the account is created, investors are ready to invest.

Select Your Portfolio and Invest

Select a portfolio from many portfolios available. Or investors can request financial experts to create a portfolio for their needs.

If investors want they can create a portfolio themselves according to the risks that they can take. Go through different mutual funds options which will show investors the returns. Investors must consider their asset allocation requirements and choose funds that suit their needs. Diversify their investment through a mutual fund which offers good returns and meets their appetite for risk.

Start the SIP

Once investors have picked the portfolio, just click on “Invest”. Rest of the process is self-explanatory.

SIP has gained momentum in the investment market when people realized that it carries lower risk. However, it must be noted that lower risk does not mean that risks are completely eliminated when investors invest through SIP. It does have its benefits of averaging the cost of purchasing the funds and it can be helpful for small investors, but it must not be considered as risk-free investments.

Best Mutual Funds For Sips In 2018? Think Again...

Scheme Name	P2P CAGR (%)	SIP XIRR (%)	Rank P2P	Rank SIP	Difference In Ranking
Aditya Birla SL India Opportunities Fund	25.52	23.77	18	39	-21
SBI Magnum MidCap Fund	25.08	24.23	21	35	-14
UTI Mid Cap Fund	26.64	25.57	13	25	-12
BNP Paribas Mid Cap Fund	24.06	24.13	25	37	-12
Tata Mid Cap Growth Fund	24.86	24.64	23	31	-8
Franklin India Smaller Cos Fund	29.20	29.18	6	11	-5
Franklin India Prima Fund	25.27	25.58	20	24	-4
ICICI Prudential Midcap Fund	25.39	25.96	19	22	-3
Edelweiss Mid and Small Cap Fund	27.46	29.08	10	12	-2
Sundaram Select Midcap	25.96	26.84	15	17	-2
Aditya Birla SL Pure Value Fund	29.42	30.91	5	6	-1
Principal Emerging Bluechip Fund	26.76	28.69	12	13	-1
HDFC Mid-Cap Opportunities Fund	25.89	26.26	17	18	-1

SBI Small & Midcap Fund	36.68	39.96	1	1	0
Reliance Small Cap Fund	35.25	36.90	2	2	0
DSPBR Micro-Cap Fund	31.85	33.38	3	3	0
Mirae Asset Emerging Bluechip	30.48	31.77	4	4	0
Canara Rob Emerging Equities Fund	29.09	30.76	7	7	0
Sundaram S.M.I.L.E Fund	27.54	29.87	9	9	0
L&T India Value Fund	25.95	27.34	16	16	0
Reliance Mid & Small Cap Fund	24.95	26.01	22	21	1
L&T Midcap Fund	28.85	31.03	8	5	3
Aditya Birla SL Small & Midcap Fund	27.34	30.05	11	8	3
HSBC Midcap Equity Fund	26.12	29.82	14	10	4
DSPBR Small & Mid Cap Fund	23.97	26.12	27	20	7
Kotak Emerging Equity Scheme	24.54	27.81	24	14	10
Tata Equity P/E Fund	23.19	26.13	31	19	12
Kotak Midcap Scheme	22.62	25.93	35	23	12
HDFC Small Cap Fund	23.52	27.38	28	15	13

Conclusion

Mutual funds give small or individual investors access to professionally managed portfolios of equities, bonds and other securities. Each shareholder, therefore, participates proportionally in the gains or losses of the fund. Mutual funds invest in a wide amount of securities, and performance is usually tracked as the change in the total market cap of the fund, derived by aggregating performance of the underlying investments. Before we invest, understand the fund's investment goals and make sure you are comfortable with the level of risk.

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